

DAMAGE RESISTANCE AND DAMAGE TOLERANCE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH DISPERSED STACKING SEQUENCES

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Abstract

The optimization of composite laminate designs towards a better impact tolerance is often overlooked in favor of efficient in-plane, statically loaded designs. This means that the response to impact damage is, in general, not accounted for in the design phase but evaluated for those designs that meet the static load requirements.

There is often margin to improve the impact response of a laminate previously designed to withstand in-plane loads in an optimal way. Using advanced optimization tools, it is possible to design alternative laminates to the ones using only 0°, 90°, and ±45° plies, that still keep the same in-plane and bending stiffness properties. In these non-conventional laminates the plies are dispersed through the [-90°,90°] range. Manufacturing of such laminates is practical nowadays as the industry switches from hand laying processes to accurate automated fiber-placement technology. By using the whole range of possible ply angles, it is possible to control at which interfaces the largest delaminations might occur and, in this way, improve the damage tolerance of a given laminate without sacrificing its stiffness.

This paper reports the design and testing (low-velocity impact and compression-after-impact) of non-conventional carbon-fiber laminates and comparisons to the performance of traditional configurations.

1 Introduction

In industrial practice the stacking sequence of laminates is often limited to combinations of 0°, 90°, ±45° fiber angle plies which is in line with the limitations of traditional layup processes in assuring

a precise fiber placement. This practice, in spite of being advantageous due to its simplicity and readiness, can be inefficient in terms of structural behavior. Although a laminate might have good specific stiffness and strength properties, it may show a poor response to impact loads. Actually, the response to impact damage is, in general, not accounted for in the early design phase but evaluated for those designs that meet the static load requirements.

Experimental research on the damage response of composite laminates has been carried by many authors (e.g. [1-5]). Cantwell and Morton [6] made an extensive review of the research work on impact damage up until 1991 and identified the fundamental parameters determining the impact resistance of CFRP's. The effect of varying fibre orientations was also addressed. In particular, the influence of the stacking sequence on the impact response of laminated composites has been studied by several authors. Dost et al. [7] investigated the damage resistance and residual strength for several quasi-isotropic laminates under low-velocity impact. Post-impact compressive behaviour was found to be a strong function of the laminate stacking sequence. Strait et al. [8] carried instrumented drop-weight impact tests on cross-ply, quasi-isotropic and 0°/±45° fibre angle based laminates. Stacking sequence was found to have a significant effect on the impact resistance, particularly at higher impact energies. Fuoss et al. [9-10] studied the influence of three parameters on the impact damage resistance of composite laminates: interface angle, ply orientation relative to a fixed axis and ply grouping. The guidelines given in their work for a better damage resistance include the avoidance of ply clustering or small interface angles.

In the previous investigations, the stacking sequence of laminates was changed with no regard for the changes in laminate stiffness. Low-velocity impact events can often be approximated to quasi-static loads. In such situations, the delaminated area is highly dependent on the out-of-plane displacement of the plate during impact [11]. This means that the bending stiffness plays an important role on the way damage develops on an impacted laminate. To avoid misinterpretations of the results, in this work both the in-plane and the bending stiffness of the studied laminates are maintained while redesigning the stacking sequence. Using advanced optimisation tools, alternatives to the traditional 0° , 90° , and $\pm 45^\circ$ fibre angle based laminates are designed where the plies are dispersed through the $]-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ fibre angle range at intervals of 5° . These non-conventional laminates (NCL) maintain similar in-plane and bending stiffness properties to the baseline from where they were derived. This procedure is possible since in the design of composite laminates, when using a sufficiently large design space, multiple optima exist i.e. there is more than one stacking sequence that satisfies a given design criterion.

This work suggests that there is margin to improve the impact response of a laminate previously designed to withstand in-plane loads in an optimal way, just by tailoring its stacking sequence. A strategy, based the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm [12-14], to optimize the low velocity impact behavior of dispersed laminates is presented. A similar strategy using Genetic Algorithms was followed previously [15] to disperse the stacking sequence of a baseline laminate with heavy ply clustering. The results of that study showed, however, a significant effect of stacking sequence dispersion on the damage resistance but negligible effect on the damage tolerance. The present strategy is validated by evaluating the response of conventional and dispersed composite laminate specimens to Low-Velocity Impact (LVI) and Compression-After-Impact (CAI) tests.

Manufacturing of laminates with dispersed stacking sequences is practical nowadays as the industry switches from hand laying processes to accurate automated fiber-placement and tape-laying technologies. Furthermore, the time and cost required to produce traditional or dispersed laminates by means of these processes are identical.

2 Impact Characterization

The impact characterization diagram proposed by Christoforou and Yigit [16] predicts the behavior type, as well as the elastic peak impact force for a wide range of impact cases. The construction of the diagram is based on simplified analytical models of the infinite plate and the quasi-static impact behaviors. Ballistic behavior is beyond the scope of the characterization diagram.

Four different regions can be identified in the diagram (Fig. 2). Impact configurations which define points in the right part of the diagram behave as quasi-static. Points that fall on or close to the dashed curve behave as infinite plate. Between the quasi-static and the infinite plate behaviors there is a transition zone where the resulting response is a combination of both. Finally, the points that fall close to the maximum dimensionless force result in the half-space behavior. The experimental validation of the characterization diagram is found in [17].

Fig. 1 Impact characterization diagram (after [16])

The curve which represents the boundary of the quasi-static response is obtained by [16]:

$$\bar{F}_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{0.68}{0.68 + \zeta_w}} \quad (1)$$

where ζ_w is the loss factor, or relative plate mobility [16], defined as:

$$\zeta_w = \frac{1}{16} \sqrt{\frac{K_\alpha M_i}{I_1 D^*}} \quad (2)$$

where K_α is the contact stiffness ($K_\alpha = 5.2R_i Y^C$ [16]), R_i is the impactor radius,

Y^C is the transverse compression strength, S^L is the in-plane shear strength, I_1 is an inertia term ($I_1 = M_p / ab$) and D^* is the plate effective bending stiffness which is defined by expressions involving elliptic functions [18]. A sufficient approximation for D^* is:

$$D^* = \sqrt{\frac{A+1}{2}} D_{11} D_{22}, \text{ where } A = \frac{D_{12} + 2D_{66}}{\sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}} \quad (3)$$

The second dimensionless parameter in Fig. 1, λ , is termed the plate relative stiffness. It can be defined as the ratio between the plate bending-shear stiffness K_{bs} and the contact stiffness K_α ($\lambda = K_{bs} / K_\alpha$). The value of the bending-shear stiffness K_{bs} can be calculated as [16]:

$$K_{bs} = \frac{D^*}{0.0116a^2} \quad (4)$$

where a is the plate length. In the case of a low velocity impact with a large mass impactor, the impact response is adequately reproduced by a simplified quasi-static impact model [16]. In such cases, the normalized impact response is governed by the single non-dimensional parameter, λ . It follows that the normalized impact force depends only on λ , and is given as [16]:

$$\bar{F}(\bar{t}) = \sqrt{\frac{1+\lambda}{\lambda}} \sin\left(\sqrt{\frac{1+\lambda}{\lambda}} \bar{t}\right) \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{F}(\bar{t})$ is the impact force normalized by the maximum impact force for a half-space behavior, given by [16]:

$$\bar{F}(\bar{t}) = \frac{F(\bar{t})}{V_0 \sqrt{M_i K_\alpha}} \quad (6)$$

where \bar{t} is the normalized contact time ($\bar{t} = \omega t$), ω is the contact frequency ($\omega = \sqrt{K_\alpha / M_i}$) and V_0 is the initial impactor velocity. From Eq. (6), the maximum normalized impact force can be obtained at $d\bar{F}/d\bar{t} = 0.0$ and $\bar{t} \neq 0.0$. The corresponding normalized time is given by:

$$\bar{t} = \frac{\pi}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1+\lambda}{\lambda}} \quad (7)$$

whereas the value of the maximum normalized force is given by:

$$\bar{F}_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{1+\lambda}} \quad (8)$$

From Eqs. (1) and (5), the limit of the quasi-static response, in terms of the two nondimensional parameters ζ_w and λ , is given as:

$$\zeta_w \geq \sqrt{\frac{0.68}{\lambda}} \quad (9)$$

2.1. Projected delamination area

The shape of a delamination is generally that of an oblong peanut, where its major axis follows the orientation of the lower ply at the interface. This shape is a result of the shear stress distribution around the surrounding area of the impactor, of the low interlaminar shear strength along or close to the direction of the fibers, and of the matrix cracks created by the flexural in-plane stresses [11].

Assuming a two-layer plate and based on the bending stiffness mismatch between the two layers, Liu [19] proposed a mismatch parameter M_L to assess the delamination area. The larger the mismatch parameter the larger the impact damage area is. This parameter is not applicable for laminated plates with more than one interface. To solve this limitation, Morita et al. [20] proposed a new parameter M_M which is calculated as:

$$M_M = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{[\Delta C_{11}(\theta) z_i]_{\max}}{D_{11}(\theta)} d\theta \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta C_{11}(\theta)$ is the difference of the in-plane stiffness between the adjacent plies in the direction θ ; z_i is the through-the-thickness distance from the neutral axis to the considered interface, and $D_{11}(\theta)$ is the bending stiffness of the entire laminate in the direction θ . A more simplified approach to calculate the projected damage was adopted by Jackson and Poe [21]. They semi-empirically correlated the projected delamination area A_d to the dimensional impact force F and the interlaminar shear strength S^L as:

$$A_d = \frac{1}{4\pi h^2} \left(\frac{F}{S^L} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

Following a similar approach, Davies and Zhang [22] proposed the following formula to the

maximum impact damage area A_d under quasi-static conditions:

$$A_d = \frac{9}{16\pi h^2} \left(\frac{F}{S^L} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

It should be noted that the delamination size predicted with Eq. (13) is 2.25 times the one predicted by Eq. (12). From Eqs. (6), (8) and (12), the maximum delamination area for a rectangular plate of thickness h under quasi-static conditions can be calculated as:

$$A_d = \frac{9\lambda M_i K_\alpha}{16\pi(1+\lambda)} \left(\frac{V_0}{hS^L} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

It is worth remarking that Eqs. (11-13) were obtained assuming a circular delamination shape and the maximum delamination is assumed to occur at the plate mid-thickness. The first assumption might in some cases be approximately accurate, when considering the projected area of several delaminations, but it is inaccurate when considering only one delamination [23]. The second assumption can be considered approximated for thick laminates but for thin ones it is not [24-25]. For these reasons the delamination area, predicted by Eq. (14), is expected to be smaller than what is obtained in experiments. Hence, in this work the value of A_d is used as a qualitative indicator of the induced damage i.e. it is not to be compared with experimental values. The higher the value of A_d , the larger the damage area, and the lower the expected impact resistance and damage tolerance.

2.2. Delamination threshold force

The loading level at which the first unstable delamination appears is usually referred to as the delamination threshold force. On the load-displacement curve this load can be considered as the first sharp decrease in the stiffness. Using the Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) for a simply supported isotropic plate under static out-of-plane loading, and assuming that only one circular midplane delamination exists, Davies et al. [26] presented an equation to predict the threshold load for delamination which, for orthotropic plates, can be written as:

$$F_{d1}^{\text{stat}} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{32D^* G_{IIc}}{3}} \quad (14)$$

wherein G_{IIc} is the fracture toughness in mode II loading and h is the plate thickness. A more rigorous solution for an arbitrary number of delaminations nd located at same intervals through-the-thickness of the plate was derived by Suemasu and Majima [27]. The threshold, in this case, is defined as:

$$F_{dn}^{\text{stat}} = \pi \sqrt{\frac{32D^* G_{IIc}}{nd+2}} \quad (15)$$

To take into account the dynamic effects in low velocity impact events, Olsson et al. [28] added a correction factor to Eq. (15). The resulting delamination threshold load was given by

$$F_{dn}^{\text{dyn}} = 1.213\pi \sqrt{\frac{32D^* G_{IIc}}{nd+2}} \quad (16)$$

for an arbitrary number of delaminations nd . For a single mid-plane delamination ($nd = 1$), Eq. (16) becomes:

$$F_{d1}^{\text{dyn}} = 1.213\pi \sqrt{\frac{32D^* G_{IIc}}{3}} \quad (17)$$

Although Eq. (18) was driven based on small mass assumptions, its predictions were in agreement with the experimental results obtained by González et al. [29] for large mass impact events, especially in cases of almost circular projected delamination areas. The normalized value of the delamination threshold can be obtained from Eq. (17) and (6) as:

$$\bar{F}_{d1}^{\text{dyn}} = \frac{F_{d1}^{\text{dyn}}}{V_0 \sqrt{M_i K_\alpha}} = \frac{F_{d1}^{\text{dyn}}}{\sqrt{2E_i K_\alpha}} \quad (18)$$

wherein $E_i = M_i g H_i = 0.5 M_i V_0^2$ is the impact energy (H_i is the impactor drop height and g is the gravity force).

3 Stacking Sequence Optimization

To improve the impact damage resistance and damage tolerance of conventional laminates, a two-step approach to the design of laminates is proposed. In the first step, the optimal laminate is designed in the traditional fashion to cope with the expected quasi-static loads on the structure. The second step consists of redesigning this laminate by dispersing

its stacking sequence. This is done without compromising the initial stiffness properties. This second stage of design is cost efficient since the candidate laminates are those with known stiffness properties, thus minimizing the number of designs for which impact testing is required.

The objective function for the optimization in the second stage of design consists in the minimization of the projected delamination area, A_d , as predicted by Eq. (14) [30]. The problem is limited to the finding of dispersed laminate solutions with similar in-plane and flexural stiffness as the baseline conventional laminate by the application of the following constrains:

$$\begin{aligned} 0.9E_y &\leq E_x \leq 1.1E_y \\ 0.9E_x^{Con} &\leq E_x \leq 1.1E_x^{Con} \\ 0.9E_{fx}^{Con} &\leq E_{fx} \leq 1.1E_{fx}^{Con} \\ 0.9E_{fy}^{Con} &\leq E_{fy} \leq 1.1E_{fy}^{Con} \end{aligned}$$

where E_x , E_y , E_{fx} and E_{fy} are the laminate in-plane and flexural stiffness moduli ($E_{fx} = 12 / (h^3 D_{11}^{-1})$ and $E_{fy} = 12 / (h^3 D_{22}^{-1})$), h is the plate thickness and D_{ij}^{-1} are the components of the compliance matrix. The superscript Con refers to baseline conventional laminate resulting from the first stage of design. The balance of the dispersed stacking sequences is guaranteed by the application of the constraint:

$$A_{16}, A_{26} \leq 0.01A_{11}$$

where A_{ij} are the components of the in-plane stiffness matrix. To achieve the symmetry, the orientation angles of one half of the laminate are used as design variables, and are then mirrored. A sixth constraint guarantees that the laminate response under low-velocity impact is quasi-static:

$$\zeta_w \geq \sqrt{\frac{0.68}{\lambda}}$$

3.1 Ant Colony Optimization (ACO)

The Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) is the algorithm used to disperse the conventional stacking sequences in an optimal way. The ACO algorithm is the simulation of the behavior of real ants when traveling between the nest and the food source. The

way in which the ant chooses a certain path depends on the relative amount of pheromone concentration on the paths. The shortest paths to the food source have higher pheromone concentrations because more ants have successfully followed those paths in previous travels [12].

In the first trip from the nest to the food source (the first optimization iteration), an equal amount of pheromone is assumed in all the available paths (stacking sequences). Due to the similar amount of pheromone in all paths, the selection of the ants to the best path (stacking sequence) is random. After the first iteration, the effort spent by each ant (the objective function) is assessed and compared with that of the other ants. Based on the comparison, the ants update the amount of pheromone on each path. A higher amount of pheromone is added to the shortest path while smaller amount is added to the longest path. After updating the pheromone matrix, the ants travel again from the nest to the food (the second iteration). The selection in this iteration is not random. It depends on the amount of pheromone in each path (the former experience of the ants). The process of traveling is repeated until all ants follow the same path. At this moment, this path is considered as the shortest path, i.e. the optimum solution. The detailed algorithm can be found in [12-14]. The criteria to calculate both the probability P of an ant k to follow one path is:

$$P_{ij}^k = \frac{\tau_{ij}^\alpha}{\sum_{i=1}^n \tau_{ij}} \quad (19)$$

where τ_{ij} are the components of the pheromone matrix, α is a parameter used to denote the degree of importance of pheromone, and n the number of available orientations. The counter i varies from 1 to n whereas j varies from 1 to the total number of ants. At each iteration a new pheromone matrix is calculated as:

$$\tau^{\text{new}} = \tau^{\text{old}} + NT \frac{f_{\text{best}}}{f_{\text{worst}}} \quad (20)$$

where NT is the number of ants that selected the orientation under consideration for the layer under consideration. The terms f_{best} and f_{worst} are the objective function values for both the shortest and the longest paths, respectively.

4 Experimental analyses

The material used in this study was the AS4D/TC350 carbon/epoxy. Fiber placement technology was used for the manufacturing of 24-ply impact and compression-after-impact test specimens with a total thickness of 4.46mm. The unidirectional material properties were measured according to the corresponding standard procedures, and are reported in [31].

The baseline conventional laminate is typically a traditional design optimized for some response characteristic such as buckling or vibration. In this study, the baseline was the common 24-ply quasi-isotropic configuration: $[45/0/-45/90]_{3s}$. In the optimized dispersed non-conventional stacking sequences the available ply orientation angles ranged from -85° to 90° with minimum jumps of 5° . The results of the optimization problem described above are plotted Fig. 2, for different impact energies. These predict that the damage area can be decreased by dispersing the stacking sequence of conventional laminates while keeping the global stiffness properties.

Fig. 2 Damage area indicator as a function of the impact energy

From the analytical formulation, it is clear that the delamination threshold is a function of the fracture toughness in mode II (G_{IIc}). As reported by Kim and Mayer [32], this property is a function of the orientation angles of the two plies adjacent to the crack plane. In the conventional laminates, the ply orientation angles are limited to 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$. This means that the interface angles between any

two adjacent plies are limited to 45° and 90° whereas, by using the dispersed orientations, the interface angles can range from 5° to 90° . It is possible that the performance can still be improved by having different G_{IIc} values at different interfaces.

On the other hand, there is the effect of ply clustering preliminary investigated in [15]. Ply clustering refers to laying a certain number of adjacent layers at the same orientation angle, yielding thick plies. These thick plies present less resistance to matrix cracking. In addition, matrix cracks often trigger delaminations which, in turn, are easier to propagate when thick plies are present. Clustering also increases the interlaminar shear stresses at the adjacent interfaces due to the increased difference in the bending stiffness between the ply groups. This increase in stress leads to larger delaminations. In addition, grouping layers with the same fiber orientation reduces the number of interfaces available for delamination. Reducing the number of the through-the-thickness locations available for delamination leads to fewer number of larger delaminations, under impact loading.

To investigate these counteracting effects, new stacking sequence optimization runs were performed where the objective is to generate alternative stacking sequences with the same D^* value, as defined by Eq. 3 while maintaining the same values of the in-plane and flexural stiffness properties as well. Two slightly different constrain cases were considered. In the first case (full dispersion), all the plies are allowed to assume dispersed ply orientation angles. In the second case, the orientation of some neighboring plies is enforced while the others are dispersed. The ply orientation enforcement has the objective of creating clusters of plies in the laminates, and hence allowing the evaluation of the effect of ply clustering in the impact response of laminates with the same in-plane and bending stiffness characteristics. The results of the impact and compression-after-impact tests on specimens with these non-conventional stacking sequences are presented in the following.

4.1 Case 1: Full Dispersion

Departing from the baseline, two dispersed ply angle configurations were generated in this case:

NC_01: $[10/35/65/85/65/35/5/-25/-35/-45/-55/-80]_s$

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NC_02:[-65/15/90/30/-45/30/-25/55/-10/70/-10/-80]_s. In NC_01, the ply mismatch angle was allowed to range between 10° and 30° whereas in NC_02 the mismatch angle ranges between 55° and 80°. Ply clustering was not allowed during the selection process to avoid the effect of a different number of interfaces.

The shape of the LVI induced damage as read by ultrasonic C-scan is shown in Fig. 3. These results are summarized in Fig. 4 where the projected delamination area is plotted as a function of the impact energy, for the three stacking sequences. For the lowest impact energy, the damaged area is similar for the three configurations. As the impact energy increases, delaminations grow larger for the NC_01 configuration than for the other two.

Fig. 3 The impact induced projected damage shape on the baseline and dispersed laminates (case 1) as identified by C-scan readings.

Fig. 4 Projected damage area as a function of the impact energy for the baseline and dispersed laminates

The through-the-thickness position of individual delaminations is shown in Fig. 5 for the BL and NC_01 specimens impacted at 20J. For the baseline configuration, delaminations are observed at all interfaces starting from interface number 5 to the interface number 11, one of the interfaces closer to the midplane (interfaces are counted from the impacted face to the back face). Due to the setup of the C-scan, interfaces before the 5th are not able to be scanned. Below the midplane, some delaminations can be observed, whereas others cannot due to the relative position and size of the different delaminations. Ply splitting, due to bending, is also evident from the delamination shape at the interface furthest away from the impact. Except for the back face splitting, delaminations at different interfaces have almost the same peanut shape and size, giving rise to the circular projected area in Fig. 2. The response is completely different for the NC_01 sample while the through-the-thickness shape of individual delaminations of NC_02 is more similar to that of BL laminate than to those of NC_01. Only three wide delaminations are observed in configuration NC_01, at interfaces 11, 18 and 19. Relatively smaller delaminations are identified at interfaces 5, 6, 7 and 8, whereas at interfaces 9 and 10 (mismatch angle of 10°) no delaminations are observed. Delaminations in these interfaces cannot be detected either because they are small and hidden by the other delaminations (at interface 5, 6, 7 and 8) or simply because they do not exist. This seems to lead to the conclusion that the layers with a small mismatch angle act as a cluster of plies.

The comparison between the three stacking sequences, based on the projected damage area indicates an advantage to the BL and NC_02 configurations. However, the advantage of one configuration over the other cannot be judged based on the damage area alone because in the impacted NC_01 specimens there are wider but fewer delaminations whereas in the BL and NC_02 specimens there are more but relatively narrow ones. The CAI strength normalized by the pristine specimen strength as function of the impact energy is shown in Fig. 6. It is shown that the relative residual strength of the dispersed laminate with small mismatch angle (NC_01) is higher than it is for the other two configurations. At 7.5J, the configuration NC_01 keeps its original strength

whereas the configurations BL and NC_02 loose about 21% and 30% of their original strength, respectively. At 20J, the configurations BL and NC_02 loose about 50% of their initial strength whereas the configuration NC_01 loses only 25%.

(a) BL ($\Delta\theta = 45^\circ$)

(b) NC_01 ($5^\circ \leq \Delta\theta \leq 30^\circ$)

Fig. 5 Through-the-thickness position of individual delaminations for the BL and NC_01 configuration impacted at 20 J.

Composites containing one or more delamination can buckle at a lower level of compressive load and this level depends on the number, size, position and shape of the delaminations in the laminated composite materials. The reason behind the improvement obtained for the NC_01 laminate in the compression after impact strength can be related to the smaller number of delaminations. Unlike the other configurations, the NC_01 laminate is divided into smaller number of thick sublaminates during the impact event. The larger thickness of the sublaminates increases the buckling load and consequently the CAI strength.

Fig. 6 Percentage of residual strength as a function of the impact energy

4.2 Case 2: Dispersion and Clustering

In this case, two dispersed stacking sequences were also designed. In the first one (NC_03) the algorithm was forced to lay four plies at 0° located at the specimen mid-plane, whereas, for the second dispersed laminae (NC_04), it was forced to construct two clusters of two plies at 0° located at the specimen outer surfaces. For both dispersed laminates, no extra clusters were allowed. The resulting lamination schemes are:

NC_03: [-40/0/35/-45/-70/90/65/70/-55/40/0₂]_s

NC_04: [0₂/55/65/80/-50/50/-80/-60/-50/20/-15]_s

In these laminates about 40% of the interfaces have ply orientation mismatch angles in the range of 5° - 30° , 40% in the range of 35° - 60° and 20% in the range of 65° - 90° .

The shapes of the projected delamination areas, resulting from the C-scan ultrasonic inspection on the impacted specimens of the BL, NC_03 and NC_04 configurations are shown in Fig. 7. These results are summarized in Fig. 8. For the lowest impact energy, the damaged area is similar for the three configurations. As the impact energy increases, delaminations grow larger for the non-conventional configurations than for the baseline.

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Fig. 7 The impact induced projected damage shape on the baseline and clustered+dispersed laminates as identified by C-scan readings.

Fig. 8 Projected damage area as a function of the impact energy for the baseline and clustered+dispersed laminates

The through-the-thickness position of individual delaminations after an impact of 25J can be seen in Fig. 9 for the three configurations. Fig. 9a represents the delaminations on the baseline laminate which are similar in shape and position to the ones shown in Fig. 5a, the major difference being the amount of ply splitting on the non-impacted face.

Unlike the conventional baseline laminate, the size of individual delaminations in dispersed laminates (both NC 03 and NC 04) is not the same at all the interfaces. In the case of clustering at the mid-plane (NC_03 in Fig. 9b), in addition to the ply splitting at the back face, three delaminations are responsible for the higher projected delamination area, compared to the baseline laminate (see Fig. 8). One of those delaminations is formed on the surface of the cluster closest to the impact point (interface 10), and might

have occurred due to the high interlaminar stresses at that interface and to the high density of matrix cracking in thick plies. The other two wide delaminations are propagated at interfaces 15 and 16, where the ply mismatch orientations are 85° and 55°. For interfaces with small mismatch angle, for example interface 7 (with 5°), the delaminations are relatively narrow. As expected, there are no delaminations propagated inside the ply clusters. For the configuration with two ply clusters at the laminate surfaces (NC_04), it is also observed that delaminations do not appear at all the interfaces, and when they appear they have nearly equal sizes. Similarly to the other samples, delaminations do not appear, or are too small, for interfaces with small mismatch angles.

Fig. 9 Through-the-thickness position of individual delaminations for the BL, NC_03 and NC_04 configurations impacted at 25 J.

From the current analysis, it is clear that the size of each individual delamination is a function of its through-the-thickness position (in general, delaminations below the midplane are wider than those located closer to the impacted surface), the mismatch angle of the interface (wider delaminations are propagated in between plies with

higher mismatch angle) and the thickness of the interfacing plies (or clusters). The thicker the plies, the higher the density of matrix cracks and the higher the interlaminar stresses are. These two factors contribute to the initiation and propagation of delaminations.

The CAI strength for the BL, NC_03 and NC_04 configurations is shown in Fig. 10. Compared to the baseline configuration, the laminate with one cluster at the middle of the specimen (NC_03) has higher values of the CAI strength at most of the examined impact energies. There is little improvement in the residual strength at low impact energies. However, for higher impact energies the improvements are as high as 20%. The reason behind this improvement is the existence of a thick cluster at the middle of the specimen with fibers oriented in the loading direction. The stiffness of this intact sublaminates delays the buckling of the total laminate improving its compression after impact strength.

Fig. 10 Residual strength as a function of the impact energy on the baseline and dispersed+clustered laminates

The improvement in residual strength in the case of ply clustering at the specimen surface (NC_04) is higher than for NC_03, up to 30% in this case. The reason of the higher residual strength, compared to the baseline configuration, is the existence of two clusters oriented at 0°, resisting the laminate global buckling. It is also clear that introducing two clusters at the laminate surfaces is better than having one at the middle. The reason behind this may be the higher bending stiffness of the surface sublaminates

compared to the one at the specimen the mid-surface which can improve the compression after impact strength.

5 Conclusions

The results presented in this paper show that it is possible to improve the damage tolerance of laminates already optimized for a certain stiffness response. This can be achieved by using the whole range of possible ply orientations i.e. by dispersing the stacking sequence. In such redesigned layups, some of the ply interfaces have low ply orientation mismatch, or even allow the forming of ply clusters, while other interfaces have large mismatch angles. It was observed that sublaminates sequences with interfaces with low mismatch orientations behave similarly to ply clusters within which no (or small) delaminations are formed. These sublaminates, if majorly oriented in the direction of the applied loading, confer the laminate a relatively high stability and compression-after-impact strength. Delaminations sufficiently large to divide the laminate in sublaminates will only occur at the interfaces with large ply orientation mismatches, the vicinity of ply clusters, and at the backface of the laminate (due to ply splitting).

The phenomenology observed in these experiments is not accounted for by existing analytical formulations, which would predict equal response for laminates with the same equivalent bending stiffness. Due to the fact that damage resistance and tolerance are the most demanding criteria in sizing several composite structures, the results of this work raise the prospects of tailoring ply sequences so that the corresponding design allowable can be increased, leading to lighter structures.

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